

Spectral Convergence Properties and Optimal Performance of Monte Carlo Functional Expansion Tallies vs. the Histogram Approximation

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we investigate asymptotic convergence properties of two methods for tallying responses in Monte Carlo neutron transport. The first method is the histogram approximation, in which particle scores generated during a Monte Carlo simulation are projected onto a piecewise-constant, histogram representation of the domain. The second employs functional expansion tallies, where scores are projected onto orthogonal basis functions, yielding a global, continuous representation across the domain. For functional expansion tallies, we recast the spectral analysis in a Sobolev framework, obtaining both upper and lower bounds on coefficient decay and, hence, on asymptotic truncation-error rates, under necessary and sufficient regularity conditions, applicable consistently across Sturm–Liouville eigenbases, though our focus here is on Legendre polynomials. Moreover, we introduce an optimality analysis that yields explicit asymptotic expressions for the optimal configurations of both methods, namely, the number of histogram bins or expansion orders that minimise total estimation error for a given particle population. These are used to quantify the asymptotic performance gain of functional expansion tallies relative to the histogram approximation in reducing total estimation error when both methods are configured optimally. Numerical results are consistent with theoretical predictions, placing the methods on a common analytical footing and providing practical guidance for method selection and tuning.

Keywords: Monte Carlo, Functional Expansion Tallies, Spectral Convergence Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

With advancements in high-performance parallel computing, the Monte Carlo (MC) framework has become a desirable tool for obtaining high-fidelity solutions of the neutron transport equation. However, a well-recognised limitation of the method is the slow convergence rate of statistical uncertainty, making it computationally intensive. It is therefore of great interest to improve the efficiency of MC simulations. The MC framework treats the phase-space continuously, enabling accurate estimates of integral responses without introducing discretisation error into the simulations. However, in many applications, we are interested in projecting integral responses onto a particular phase-space parameter, such as position, energy, or angle. The standard procedure is to partition the phase-space into a histogram, mapping particle scores to their appropriate phase-space bins, and is known as the histogram approximation (HA). By discretising the tally domain onto which we wish to project, however, discretisation error is inevitably incurred, and while increasing the resolution of the histogram reduces discretisation error, it simultaneously increases the statistical error each bin-estimate sees. Another approach for approximating the target distribution is through functional expansion tallies (FETs), which employ basis function expansions to form a continuous, global representation of the distribution. Analogously to HA, increasing the expansion order decreases truncation error, but also increases statistical noise embedded in the expansion coefficient estimates.

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Previous work [1] derived asymptotic bounds on the truncation error for Legendre FETs and the HA discretisation error, showing that the former can converge faster. We extend that work by recasting the spectral analysis in a Sturm–Liouville framework, yielding sharper convergence-rate bounds under necessary and sufficient regularity conditions that hold consistently across classical orthogonal polynomial Sturm–Liouville eigenbases (including Legendre). Furthermore, we derive asymptotic expressions for the optimal number of histogram bins for HA and expansion order for FETs that minimise total estimation error. With these results, we establish a unified framework to compare the two methods under their respective optimal configurations, thereby identifying regimes in which each method should be selected to minimise achievable estimation error. We validate the theory with numerical results.

2. THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF CONVERGENCE RATES

We denote the true target function, which we wish to estimate, as $f : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, operating on some domain $\mathcal{D} = [x_{\min}, x_{\max}]$.

2.1. Truncation Error of Functional Expansion Estimates

Let $\{\psi_k\}_{k=0}^{\infty}$ denote a complete orthogonal set in $L^2_{\rho}(\mathcal{D})$. Any $f \in L^2_{\rho}(\mathcal{D}) := \{f : \|f\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2 < \infty\}$, i.e., square-integrable with weighting function ρ over domain \mathcal{D} , can be expanded as follows:

$$f = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \alpha_k h_k \psi_k : \alpha_k = \int_{\mathcal{D}} f(x) \psi_k(x) \rho(x) dx \text{ and } h_k = \frac{1}{\|\psi_k\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2}, \quad (1)$$

where α_k is the functional expansion coefficient of order k , and h_k serves as a normalisation factor. If we expand the target function through a finite number of basis functions, using a maximum order K , $f_K = \sum_{k=0}^K \alpha_k h_k \psi_k$ represents the deterministic truncation of the full expansion in Eq. (1). The corresponding squared L^2 -norm of the truncation error (from neglecting higher order terms) is given by:

$$\|E_K\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2 = \int_{\mathcal{D}} (f(x) - f_K(x))^2 \rho(x) dx = \sum_{k=K+1}^{\infty} \alpha_k^2 h_k. \quad (2)$$

2.1.1. Decay Rate of Functional Expansion Coefficients

To address the decay rate of the expansion coefficients, i.e., the rate at which the magnitudes of the coefficients decrease with expansion order (which governs the truncation error, see Eq. (2)), we begin by considering the Sturm–Liouville problem [2], which can be written in terms of the Sturm–Liouville differential operator:

$$\mathcal{L} : \psi(x) \mapsto \mathcal{L}[\psi](x) := -\frac{d}{dx} \left(\bar{\delta}(x) \frac{d\psi(x)}{dx} \right) + \kappa(x) \psi(x) = \lambda \rho(x) \psi(x), \quad (3)$$

where $\bar{\delta}(x)$ is the leading coefficient, $\kappa(x)$ is the potential function, $\rho(x)$ is the weighting function, which depend on the basis $\psi(x)$. Defining the fully self-adjoint Sturm–Liouville operator as $\mathcal{L}_{\rho} := \frac{1}{\rho} \mathcal{L}$, bases that are solutions to the Sturm–Liouville equation satisfy the following eigenvalue problem:

$$\langle \mathcal{L}_{\rho}[\psi_k], \phi \rangle_{\mathcal{D},\rho} = \lambda_k \langle \psi_k, \phi \rangle_{\mathcal{D},\rho}, \quad \forall \phi \in L^2_{\rho}(\mathcal{D}). \quad (4)$$

Thus, applying the operator \mathcal{L}_{ρ} to f , as defined in Eq. (1), and performing a functional expansion thereof in $L^2_{\rho}(\mathcal{D})$, yields:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\rho}[f](x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\langle \mathcal{L}_{\rho}[f], \psi_k \rangle_{\mathcal{D},\rho}}{\|\psi_k\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2} \psi_k(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \lambda_k \alpha_k h_k \psi_k(x) \implies \mathcal{L}_{\rho}^{s/2}[f](x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \lambda_k^{s/2} \alpha_k h_k \psi_k(x), \quad (5)$$

where we used the self-adjoint and linear property of the Sturm–Liouville operator, as well as the orthogonality of the basis ψ_k . Moreover, applying Parseval’s identity, it follows that:

$$\|\mathcal{L}_\rho^{s/2} f\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2 = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\left| \langle \mathcal{L}_\rho^{s/2} [f], \psi_k \rangle_{\mathcal{D},\rho} \right|^2}{\|\psi_k\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \lambda_k^s \alpha_k^2 h_k. \quad (6)$$

We can then look at for what orders of α_k Eq. (6) is at the threshold of divergence. We can use the p -series test to determine this. The p -series is given by $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k^{-p}$, which converges for $p > 1$ and diverges for $p \leq 1$. Hence, assuming power-law asymptotics where $\exists A_1, A_2, A_3 > 0$ and exponents ξ, η, ζ such that $\lambda_k \sim A_1 k^\xi$, $h_k \sim A_2 k^\eta$, and $\alpha_k \sim A_3 k^\zeta$:

$$\|\mathcal{L}_\rho^{s/2} f\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2 < \infty \iff \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \lambda_k^s \alpha_k^2 h_k < \infty \iff |\alpha_k| < \frac{1}{\lambda_k^{s/2} h_k^{1/2} k^{1/2}} = \Theta(k^{-s\xi/2 - \eta/2 - 1/2}), \quad (7)$$

where, here and throughout this paper, $\Theta(v) := \{\tau(v) : \exists C_1, C_2 > 0, v_0 \in \mathbb{R} \text{ such that } C_1|v| \leq |\tau(v)| \leq C_2|v| \forall v \geq v_0\}$, and we use $\Theta(\cdot)$ to compare asymptotic orders rather than pointwise values. Accordingly, any expressions involving $\Theta(\cdot)$ throughout this paper are to be interpreted in the asymptotic order sense. From Eq. (7), $|\alpha_k| = \Theta(k^{-s\xi/2 - \eta/2 - 1/2})$ is the smallest order that results in divergence, any strictly faster power-law decay such that $\zeta < -s\xi/2 - \eta/2 - 1/2$ yields convergence. Thus, we can obtain a strict upper bound on the decay rate, depending on λ_k and h_k , which are inherent properties of the basis considered. To establish the sharp threshold on coefficient decay, we must determine when $\|\mathcal{L}_\rho^{s/2} f\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2$ transitions from finite to infinite, a transition that depends on the regularity conditions we assume about f , and will now be related to the Sturm–Liouville operator. Consider the Legendre polynomials [3], where $\delta(x) = 1 - x^2$, $\kappa(x) = 0$, and $\rho(x) = 1$ (hence, $\mathcal{L}_\rho \equiv \mathcal{L}$). From Eq. (3), we get:

$$\mathcal{L}_\rho := -\frac{d}{dx} \left((1 - x^2) \frac{d}{dx} \right) \xrightarrow{\text{apply to } f} \mathcal{L}_\rho[f](x) = 2x f^{(1)}(x) - (1 - x^2) f^{(2)}(x). \quad (8)$$

Using an induction argument, followed by repeated integration by parts on Eq. (8) (proof omitted for brevity), it can be shown that $\|\mathcal{L}_\rho^{s/2} f\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2$ is finite whenever $f^{(j)} \in L_\rho^2(\mathcal{D}), \forall j = 1, \dots, s$. Conversely, if, for some $j \leq s$, $f^{(j)} \notin L_\rho^2(\mathcal{D})$, then $\|\mathcal{L}_\rho^{s/2} f\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2$ necessarily diverges (assuming derivatives of f up to order s have no endpoint singularities). Thus, a lower bound for the decay rate of $|\alpha_k|$ is such that the squared L^2 -norm of $f^{(s)}$ diverges, meaning $f^{(s)} \notin L_\rho^2(\mathcal{D})$. We define the smoothness index $s \in \mathbb{N}$ in this framework as the smallest integer such that $f \in H_\rho^{s-1}(\mathcal{D}) \setminus H_\rho^s(\mathcal{D})$, where the weighted Hilbert space is defined as:

$$H_\rho^s \equiv W_\rho^{s,2}(\mathcal{D}) := \left\{ f \in L_\rho^2(\mathcal{D}) \mid f^{(j)} \in L_\rho^2(\mathcal{D}), \forall j = 1, \dots, s \right\}, \quad (9)$$

and corresponds to the weighted Sobolev space, $W_\rho^{s,p}$, when the order of integrability is $p = 2$. For functions $f \in H_\rho^{s-1}(\mathcal{D}) \setminus H_\rho^s(\mathcal{D})$, the s^{th} derivative of f diverges in Eq. (7), whereas the $(s - 1)^{\text{th}}$ derivative remains bounded, as do all lower-order derivatives. This can be used to obtain an asymptotically sharp band for the decay rate of the coefficients, that is: $\Theta((\lambda_k)^{-s/2} (h_k)^{-1/2} k^{-1/2}) \leq |\alpha_k| < \Theta((\lambda_k)^{-(s-1)/2} (h_k)^{-1/2} k^{-1/2})$. For instance, in the case of the Legendre basis, with corresponding $\lambda_k = k(k + 1)$ and $h_k = \frac{2k+1}{2}$, we obtain the following asymptotic band for the expansion coefficients:

$$\Theta(k^{-s-1}) \leq |\alpha_k| < \Theta(k^{-s}). \quad (10)$$

In this way, the condition $f \in H_\rho^{s-1}(\mathcal{D}) \setminus H_\rho^s(\mathcal{D})$ is both necessary and sufficient for the Legendre coefficients to decay within the asymptotically narrow band of $|\alpha_k| \in [\Theta(k^{-s-1}), \Theta(k^{-s})]$, where the inclusive lower bound guarantees non-membership in $H_\rho^s(\mathcal{D})$, while the strict upper bound corresponds to membership in $H_\rho^{s-1}(\mathcal{D})$.

2.1.2. L^2 -norm Truncation Error

Using the Legendre coefficient decay rate bounds in Eq. (10), we can obtain a band for the convergence of the squared L^2 -norm truncation error. We apply the approximation $\sum_{k=K+1}^{\infty} k^{-p} \approx (p-1)^{-1} K^{-p+1}$, which has been shown to hold [4] for $K \gg 1$, and $p > 1$, to Eq. (2), yielding the asymptotic result:

$$\Theta((2s)^{-1} K^{-2s}) \leq \|E_K\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2 < \Theta((2s-2)^{-1} K^{-2s+2}) \implies \|E_K\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho} \in [\Theta(K^{-s}), \Theta(K^{-s+1})], \quad (11)$$

assuming $s > 1$, otherwise the infinite sum in Eq. (2) diverges for the strict upper bound.

2.2. Discretisation Error of the Histogram Approximation

By uniformly partitioning our domain $\mathcal{D} = [x_{\min}, x_{\max}]$ into T bins, $I = \{[x_b, x_{b+1}]\}_{b=1}^T$, we can deterministically represent HA as a step-function approximation of f :

$$f_T(x) = \sum_{b=1}^T \bar{f}_b \mathbb{1}(x \in I_b), \quad \bar{f}_b = \frac{1}{x_{b+1} - x_b} \int_{x_b}^{x_{b+1}} f(x) dx, \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbb{1}(\cdot)$ denotes the indicator function. This is analogous to f_K , which we defined earlier as the deterministic truncation of a functional expansion of f . It has been shown [1] that, assuming a uniform tally grid (noting that for HA we take $\rho(x) = 1$):

$$\sqrt{\|E_T\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2} = \sqrt{\int_{\mathcal{D}} (f(x) - f_T(x))^2 dx} = \Theta\left(\frac{1}{T}\right). \quad (13)$$

2.3. Stochastic Uncertainty under Finite Monte Carlo Sampling

In MC neutron transport, sampled particle scores are tallied (e.g., via the collision estimator [5]) and then projected to form estimates of the response f . For FETs, scores are projected onto the basis to form mean estimates of the expansion coefficients $\hat{\alpha}_k$, yielding \hat{f}_K . For HA, scores are accumulated in histogram bins and averaged to produce \hat{f}_T :

$$\hat{f}_K(x) = \sum_{k=0}^K \hat{\alpha}_k h_k \psi_k(x) \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{f}_T(x) = f_T(x) + \sum_{b=1}^T \varepsilon_b \mathbb{1}(x \in I_b) : \varepsilon_b \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_b^2). \quad (14)$$

The estimates are stochastic and have uncertainties associated with them. Given a finite number of particle histories N , the expected L^2 -norm statistical errors for FETs and HA can be shown [1] to satisfy:

$$\sqrt{\mathbb{E}[\|E_{K,\text{stat}}\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2]} \leq \Theta\left(\sqrt{\frac{K}{N}}\right) \quad \text{and} \quad \sqrt{\mathbb{E}[\|E_{T,\text{stat}}\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2]} = \Theta\left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{N}}\right). \quad (15)$$

2.4. Optimal Trade-off Between Approximation Error and Stochastic Noise

From the previous sections, there is a trade-off between truncation error for FETs, discretisation error for HA, and statistical error. This implies that, for a given number of particle histories, N , there exists an optimal maximum expansion order K^* for FETs that minimises the (squared) total L^2 -norm error $\|E_{\text{total, FET}}\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2 = \|E_K\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2 + \mathbb{E}[\|E_{K,\text{stat}}\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2]$. Similarly, for HA there is an optimal number of bins T^* which minimises $\|E_{\text{total, HA}}\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2 = \|E_T\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2 + \mathbb{E}[\|E_{T,\text{stat}}\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2]$. Asymptotically, as $T, K \rightarrow \infty$, statistical error dominates and scales equivalently for FETs and HA (Eq. (15)), thus, no method sees a gain in performance relative to the other in reducing the total error. Any gain from using FETs comes from faster

convergence of the truncation error relative to the discretisation error in HA, both of which dominate for small K and T . We now derive the optimal maximum expansion order $K^* := \arg \min_K \|E_{\text{total, FET}}\|_{\mathcal{D}, \rho}^2$. Using the lower bound L^2 -norm truncation error in Eq. (11) for the Legendre basis, we conduct the following asymptotic (with respect to N) optimisation:

$$\frac{d}{dK} \|E_{\text{total, FET}}\|_{\mathcal{D}, \rho}^2 \Big|_{K^*} = 0 \iff \frac{d}{dK} \left[\Theta\left(\frac{1}{K^{2s}}\right) + \Theta\left(\frac{K}{N}\right) \right] \Big|_{K^*} = 0 \iff K_l^* = \Theta\left(N^{\frac{1}{2s+1}}\right), \quad (16)$$

which can be proven to be a minimum since $\frac{d^2}{dK^2} \|E_{\text{total, FET}}\|_{\mathcal{D}, \rho}^2 \Big|_{K_l^*} = \Theta\left(N^{-\frac{2(s+1)}{2s+1}}\right) > 0, \forall s > 0$. Applying the same procedure to the strict upper bound gives $K_u^* = \Theta\left(N^{1/(2s-1)}\right)$, hence:

$$K^* \in [K_l^*, K_u^*] = [\Theta\left(N^{1/(2s+1)}\right), \Theta\left(N^{1/(2s-1)}\right)]. \quad (17)$$

Applying the analogous procedure to HA yields:

$$\frac{d}{dT} \|E_{\text{total, HA}}\|_{\mathcal{D}, \rho}^2 \Big|_{T^*} = 0 \iff \frac{d}{dT} \left[\Theta\left(\frac{1}{T^2}\right) + \Theta\left(\frac{T}{N}\right) \right] \Big|_{T^*} = 0 \iff T^* = \Theta\left(N^{1/3}\right). \quad (18)$$

Hence, the smoother the target function, the further K^* drops below T^* , and we generally expect $K^* < T^*$. Substituting in K^* for the Legendre basis, we obtain the following bounds on optimal (minimum) squared total L^2 -norm error:

$$\min_K \|E_{\text{total, FET}}\|_{\mathcal{D}, \rho}^2 \in \left[\Theta\left(K_l^{*(-2s)} + \frac{K_l^*}{N}\right), \Theta\left(K_u^{*(-2s+2)} + \frac{K_u^*}{N}\right) \right] = \left[\Theta\left(N^{\frac{1}{2s+1}-1}\right), \Theta\left(N^{\frac{1}{2s-1}-1}\right) \right]. \quad (19)$$

Substituting in T^* for HA, the corresponding optimal squared total L^2 -norm error reads:

$$\min_T \|E_{\text{total, HA}}\|_{\mathcal{D}, \rho}^2 = \Theta\left(\frac{1}{T^{*2}}\right) + \Theta\left(\frac{T^*}{N}\right) = \Theta\left(N^{-2/3}\right). \quad (20)$$

Noting that both expressions for the optimal squared total L^2 -norm error in Eqs. (19) and (20) are written in terms of N , we can explicitly compare the total L^2 -norm error of HA and FET under optimal usage. We define the gain in optimal total L^2 -norm error as:

$$G_{\text{total}}^* = \sqrt{\frac{\min_T \|E_{\text{total, HA}}\|_{\mathcal{D}, \rho}^2}{\min_K \|E_{\text{total, FET}}\|_{\mathcal{D}, \rho}^2}} \in \left(\Theta\left(N^{-\frac{1}{3} + \frac{s-1}{2s-1}}\right), \Theta\left(N^{-\frac{1}{3} + \frac{s}{2s+1}}\right) \right], \quad (21)$$

where $G_{\text{total}}^* > 1$ indicates a ‘‘positive’’ performance gain for Legendre FET relative to HA, in the sense that it reduces the total L^2 -norm error and hence the root-mean-square error (RMSE), which is proportional to the total L^2 -norm error. Thus, the smoother the function f , the higher the performance gain of Legendre FET relative to HA, and when both methods are configured optimally, we generally expect a positive performance gain for Legendre FET.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

We validate the theoretical convergence rates on simple toy problems, where target functions and regularities are known in closed form, though the theory extends more generally to stochastic spectral estimators across a wide range of applications, such as MC neutron transport, which will be addressed in an upcoming journal paper. Figure 1a shows the target function $f_1(x)$ together with its first two

Figure 1. Target functions f_1 and f_2 along with their piecewise derivatives on $x \in [-1, 1]$.

piecewise derivatives. In the Sobolev framework, $f_1''(x) = 2\delta(x)$ is the first derivative order that fails to be square-integrable ($\delta(x) \notin L^2(\mathcal{D})$), so $f_1 \in H_\rho^1(\mathcal{D}) \setminus H_\rho^2(\mathcal{D})$, i.e., $s = 2$. In Figure 1b we see $f_2(x)$ together with its first three piecewise derivatives, and by the same argument, $s = 3$ in this case.

As the functions are known in closed form, we can compute exact expansion coefficients α_k (see Eq. (1)) and thereby construct the deterministically truncated expansion f_K for a given maximum order K , and investigate noise-free truncation error convergence. Likewise, for HA, given T tally bins, we integrate f over each bin to obtain the deterministic histogram representation f_T (see Eq. (12)). Plugging $s = 2$ and $s = 3$ into Eq. (10) yields the coefficient decay bounds $\alpha_k^{s=2} \in [\Theta(k^{-3}), \Theta(k^{-2})]$ and $\alpha_k^{s=3} \in [\Theta(k^{-4}), \Theta(k^{-3})]$. Figure 2 shows that the Legendre coefficients lie comfortably within each respective Sobolev band. Moreover, substituting $s = 2$ and $s = 3$ into Eq. (11) gives the L^2 -norm truncation error bounds $\|E_K\|_{\mathcal{D}, \rho}^{s=2} \in [\Theta(K^{-2}), \Theta(K^{-1})]$ and $\|E_K\|_{\mathcal{D}, \rho}^{s=3} \in [\Theta(K^{-3}), \Theta(K^{-2})]$. Figure 3 reports RMSE vs. T for HA and vs. K for Legendre FET. Again, the results lie comfortably within their respective Sobolev bands, and converge faster than the $\Theta(1/T)$ discretisation error rate for HA (Eq. (13)). Note that, since there is no statistical noise, RMSE decreases monotonically with T and K , i.e., there is no noise floor.

Figure 2. Legendre coefficients α_k vs. order k .

Figure 3. RMSE vs. T (HA) and K (Legendre FET).

We now examine finite-sampling effects by drawing N MC samples from the distributions f_1 and f_2 , forming \hat{f}_T , i.e., per-bin sample means for HA and \hat{f}_K via sample-mean coefficients $\hat{\alpha}_k$ for Legendre FET (Eq. (14)). Unless stated otherwise, $N = 1 \times 10^5$. Figure 4 shows the mean Legendre coefficient estimates $\hat{\alpha}_k$ in both cases, which match the deterministic results in Figure 2 when the fit window is restricted to the pre-knee regions. Figure 5 shows the corresponding RMSE curves. In this case, a signal-to-noise

knee appears as T or K increases, limiting the minimum achievable RMSE. Nevertheless, the Legendre FET error rates remain within the respective Sobolev bands for $\|E_K\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^{s=2}$ and $\|E_K\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^{s=3}$ when fitting on the pre-knee regions, and HA continues to follow the $\Theta(1/T)$ rate, independent of s . The noise-dominated tails follow the expected asymptotics, with HA growing like \sqrt{T} and FET like \sqrt{K} (see Eq. (15)).

Figure 4. Sample-based Legendre coefficient estimates, \hat{a}_k , vs. expansion order k . Figure 5. Sample-based RMSE vs. T (HA) and K (Legendre FET).

For the remaining studies we use 1000 repetitions and report ± 2 standard deviations. The parametric sweep in N is shown in Figures 6a and 6b for HA and Legendre FET, respectively, for f_1 . Increasing N drives the signal-to-noise knee down, and we record the resulting optimal configurations and corresponding RMSE. The same procedure is applied for f_2 . Figure 7a shows the empirical optimal configurations \hat{T}^* (HA) and \hat{K}^* (Legendre FET) vs. N . HA agrees with the theoretically derived rate $T^* = \Theta(N^{1/3})$ (see Eq. (18)) in both cases. For Legendre FET with $s = 2$ (f_1), the observed \hat{K}^* lies within the theoretical Sobolev band from Eq. (17), $K^{* s=2} \in [\Theta(N^{1/5}), \Theta(N^{1/3})]$. As expected, $\hat{K}^* < \hat{T}^*$ as Legendre FET converges faster than HA. In the case of $s = 3$ (f_2), the observed rate lies within the Sobolev band $K^{* s=3} \in [\Theta(N^{1/7}), \Theta(N^{1/5})]$, as expected as a lower order is required to capture the smoother underlying distribution. The optimal RMSE vs. N is shown in Figure 7b. HA satisfies Eq. (20), i.e., the derived optimal L^2 -norm error rate $\sqrt{\min_T \|E_{\text{total, HA}}\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^2} = \Theta(N^{-1/3})$ in both cases, while Legendre FET decays faster, consistent with Eq. (19) at $s = 2$ (f_1), $\sqrt{\min_K \|E_{\text{total, FET}}\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^{2, s=2}} \in [\Theta(N^{-2/5}), \Theta(N^{-1/3})]$, again within the Sobolev band. At $s = 3$ (f_2) we observe an even faster convergence rate, within the theoretical Sobolev band $\sqrt{\min_K \|E_{\text{total, FET}}\|_{\mathcal{D},\rho}^{2, s=3}} \in [\Theta(N^{-3/7}), \Theta(N^{-2/5})]$, and is consistent with smoother functions yielding faster error convergence. Finally, the gain under optimal configurations in Figure 7c lies comfortably within the Sobolev band in Eq. (21) for $s = 2$ (f_1), $G_{\text{total}}^{* s=2} \in (\Theta(N^0), \Theta(N^{1/15}))$. At $s = 3$ (f_2), a higher gain rate can be observed, which lies within the theoretical Sobolev band $G_{\text{total}}^{* s=3} \in (\Theta(N^{1/15}), \Theta(N^{2/21}))$, supporting the theoretical predictions and is consistent with higher performance gain the smoother the underlying distribution.

Figure 6. Parametric study of the effect of sample size N on RMSE (f_1).

Figure 7. Parametric study of the effect of sample size N on optimal configurations, RMSE, and gain.

4. CONCLUSION

We presented a general framework for spectral analysis of FETs and HA in the context of MC sampling. Within a Sobolev framework, we established necessary and sufficient regularity conditions and derived corresponding bounds on expansion coefficient decay rate and asymptotic L^2 -norm truncation error convergence for the Legendre basis. We also introduced an optimality analysis that provides a practical rule for optimally configuring both methods for a given sample size, and quantified the theoretical gain of FETs over HA when both are configured optimally. Empirical results showed excellent agreement with the theoretical derivations presented in this work, confirming that even in the theoretically worst-case scenario for FETs, we expect a slight edge in performance relative to HA. Finally, future work will extend the study to other Sturm–Liouville eigenbases and to D -dimensional tallies in MC neutron transport problems, i.e., joint tallies over a D -dimensional phase-space domain, using tensor-product histograms and tensor-product expansions with one-dimensional bases (e.g., Legendre) applied separately in each coordinate.

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